

PERSEPHONE

Grant agreement no.	101138451
Project acronym	PERSEPHONE
Project full title	Autonomous Exploration and Extraction of Deep Mineral Deposits
Dissemination level	PU Public
Date of Delivery	30 06 2025
Deliverable Number	D10.2
Deliverable Name	Initial report on open data releases, data management, innovation management and IP protection
AL / Task related	T10.2
Author/s	Anton Koval (LTU), Sumeet Gajanan Satpute (LTU)
Contributors	All partners
Reviewer	George Nikolakopoulos (LTU), Pär-Erik Martinsson (LTU)
Keywords	Data management, Innovation management, IP protection
Abstract	This deliverable outlines the initial strategy and governance framework for managing innovation, open access, and intellectual property within the PERSEPHONE project. It describes how the consortium aligns with FAIR data principles, supports public dissemination of research assets

History of Changes

Version	Date	Reason of change
V0.1 (draft)	30 June 2025	The initial draft of the document is ready and ready for distribution between PERSEPHONE project partners to review.
V0.5	25 July 2025	Final draft ready to be reviewed
V1.0	30 July 2025	Final version ready

Executive summary

This deliverable provides an initial overview of the actions undertaken within the PERSEPHONE project to ensure research transparency, data accessibility, and innovation readiness. It outlines the project's alignment with FAIR data principles, the release of simulation environments and real-world datasets, and the processes established to manage intellectual property and innovation assets. Furthermore, it introduces the Intellectual Property Office (IPO) and Innovation Management Office (IMO), and their roles in supporting IP protection and exploitation. These efforts lay the groundwork for successful technology transfer, open science dissemination, and structured exploitation in line with Horizon Europe guidelines.

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon Europe Research and Innovation Programme under the Grant Agreement No.101138451

Table of content

Table of content	3
1 Abbreviations.....	4
2 Introduction.....	5
2.1 Purpose and scope of the document	5
2.2 Objective.....	5
2.3 Related documents	5
3 Data Management and Open Science practices.....	6
3.1 Alignment with FAIR Principles.....	6
3.1.1 Public release of the Simulation environment.....	6
3.1.2 Open Source Dataset for Underground Mines.....	9
3.2 Types of Data Collected and Released	10
3.3 Metadata and Interoperability Standards.....	10
3.4 Data Review and Release Process	11
4 Innovation Management	12
4.1 Background IP.....	13
4.2 Foreground IP	13
4.3 Commercial Rights and Stakeholder Involvement.....	13
5 Conclusions.....	15

1 Abbreviations

Abbreviations	
AI	Artificial Intelligence
CA	Consortium Agreement
CSV	Comma-Separated Values
DMP	Data Management Plan
DOI	Digital Object Identifier
FAIR	Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, and Reusable
GIS	Geographic Information System
GM	Grecian Magnesite
IPR	Intellectual Property Rights
IPO	Intellectual Property Office
IMO	Innovation Management Office
KER	Key Exploitable Result
LiDAR	Light Detection and Ranging
LTU	Luleå University of Technology
RAI	Robotics and AI Group at LTU
RGB-D	Red Green Blue with Depth
ROS	Robot Operating System
SaaS	Software as a Service
SDF	Simulation Description Format
SME	Small and Medium-sized Enterprises
TTO	Technology Transfer Office
TRL	Technology Readiness Level
URDF	Unified Robot Description Format
WP	Work Package

2 Introduction

2.1 Purpose and scope of the document

This deliverable presents initial summary of the actions towards ensuring research verifiability/reproducibility of the PERSEPHONE results, such as open releases of data from lab experiments/ small scale field tests. Details about the establishment of Intellectual Property Office (IPO) and Innovation Management Office (IMO) and innovation support tools for the protection of the partners' IPs.

2.2 Objective

The objective of this deliverable is to provide an initial summary of the actions undertaken to ensure the verifiability and reproducibility of the research results generated within the PERSEPHONE project. This includes documentation of open data releases from laboratory experiments and small-scale field tests, which support transparency and scientific integrity.

Additionally, the deliverable outlines the establishment and roles of the Intellectual Property Office (IPO) and the Innovation Management Office (IMO), detailing their collaborative framework for managing intellectual property and innovation. It also presents an overview of the innovation support tools employed to safeguard the partners' IPs and facilitate strategic exploitation planning in alignment with Horizon Europe guidelines.

2.3 Related documents

This deliverable is part of the project's overarching communication, dissemination, and exploitation work package (WP10) and complements other related deliverables, such as D10.1 (that details dissemination and communication strategy) and D10.3 (that details actions on exploitation and engagement with end users).

3 Data Management and Open Science practices

Ensuring the accessibility, transparency, and reproducibility of research outputs is a core objective of the PERSEPHONE project. To this end, the consortium has implemented a structured data management approach in alignment with the FAIR principles—making data Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, and Reusable. The data strategy has been embedded from the start of the project to support scientific credibility, cross-WP collaboration, and future exploitation of key results.

3.1 Alignment with FAIR Principles

The PERSEPHONE project is fully committed to managing all research data in accordance with the FAIR principles, Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, and Reusable, as outlined in the project’s data management plan (see D10.5). These principles guide the treatment of both experimental and simulation-generated data across all technical work packages (WPs), ensuring transparency, reproducibility, and long-term value creation.

To support compliance with FAIR, each WP has implemented shared practices such as consistent file naming conventions, metadata standards, and structured file organization. Data are stored in secure, partner-level or institutional repositories, with selected outputs being curated for publication via recognized open-access platforms, particularly Zenodo and GitHub, which support version control and DOI assignment.

In line with this commitment, PERSEPHONE has established a dedicated Zenodo community repository for archiving project outputs, [Link](#). This repository will host:

- Open-access research publications
- Validated simulation and experimental datasets (e.g., sensor logs, robot test runs)
- Simulation data from Gazebo, Unity, or planning tools
- Associated documentation and metadata to support reproducibility

The overarching goal of this repository is to ensure that all publicly shareable research outcomes are easily accessible and citable, in full support of open science and reproducibility.

3.1.1 Public release of the Simulation environment

As part of PERSEPHONE’s commitment to open science, technology transfer, and long-term impact, the consortium is preparing for the public release of the simulation environment developed under WP8. This environment supports the integrated testing, validation, and demonstration of multiple PERSEPHONE Key Exploitable Results (KERs) and has played a critical role in enabling iterative development across WP2–WP7.

The environment is described in detail in Deliverable D8.2 – Realistic Simulation Worlds for Integrated Testing of PERSEPHONE Technologies, which outlines the

system architecture, environment modelling process, and ROS2/Gazebo-based deployment stack. The deliverable will be made public and will act as a guideline document to use the simulation environment. This developed environment includes:

- High-resolution underground mine environments reconstructed from LiDAR scans and RGB-D imaging from the GM's abandoned underground magnesite mine (Figure 1) and the LTU-RAI's SubT underground test laboratory
- Various mining environment areas such as rockfall, mine-deformation, variable traversable terrains, realistic ore mineral textured areas, (see Figure 2) etc.
- Modular robotic models (URDF) representing autonomous mining machines (e.g., the deployer, supplier robots, etc)
- Sensor suite mounted on the robot and includes IMU, RGB-D camera, LiDAR (ref. Figure 3), etc.

Figure 1: The original point cloud LAS scan from the GM mine is converted into a mesh format for further integration into Gazebo as a simulation world.

a)

b)

Figure 2: Different underground mine simulation scenarios a) Rockfall, b) deformed tunnel, c) untraversable tunnel and d) realistic magnesite vein walls for ore detection simulations

Figure 3: Rviz visualization of the sensor data while the deployer and supplier robots are moving through the simulated tunnel

To maximise reuse and accessibility, the simulation stack is being packaged for open release on GitHub and/or Zenodo, including:

- Core simulation worlds (.world and .sdf files)
- Pre-configured robot and sensor packages
- Launch files for running world and robot model
- Documentation and usage tutorials

The release is planned under an open-source license for research use, with appropriate attribution to the PERSEPHONE project and partners. Selected modules developed by individual partners may be released under dual-licensing models or with attribution-only clauses, depending on IPR status (as will be coordinated under WP11).

The simulation environment supports three key goals:

- Enable continued research and benchmarking of autonomous mining systems in academic and industrial settings
- Facilitate training and education on digital mining, autonomy, and multi-sensor integration

- Support technology transfer by allowing external stakeholders to reproduce test conditions and evaluate KERs in controlled environments

This open release reflects PERSEPHONE's broader exploitation strategy to share foundational tools while protecting commercially sensitive components. It will be announced and disseminated via the project website, social media, and during upcoming events and workshops as a part of WP11.

3.1.2 Open Source Dataset for Underground Mines

Apart from the Gazebo based simulation environment, the consortium, with the due approval of GM, is also preparing to release a curated open-source dataset capturing sensor and environmental data from the GM abandoned underground mine. This dataset is intended to support researchers, developers, and educators working in underground mining-related domains by providing access to high-quality, real-world data. It also aims to foster open innovation, promote reproducibility, and encourage community engagement within the fields of robotics, geoscience, and mining systems.

This release directly supports the objectives outlined in D2.4 – Real-time Sensing and Sensor Integration, which identified the need for public datasets to simulate and evaluate synthetic sensor data under mine-like conditions (ref. Figure 4). It also complements the simulation environment release from WP8, enabling a holistic, data-driven development ecosystem for underground automation. Thus, this dataset provides realistic foundation for:

- Benchmarking autonomous navigation algorithms
- Training and evaluating sensor fusion pipelines
- Generating synthetic datasets for AI/ML development in subterranean robotics
- Supporting academic publications, teaching modules, hackathons, etc.

The dataset will be hosted on a Zenodo repository, with links to associated GitHub simulation environments.

Figure 4: Model update simulation in Leapfrog Geo from deliverable D2.4. The figure illustrates how block models are updated using new information, in this case magnesite %, as 'synthetic data' is generated. The example shown uses fictive multispectral input to simulate the update process.

3.2 Types of Data Collected and Released

PERSEPHONE will produce a range of data during the integration and demonstration phase of the project which includes:

- Sensor datasets
- Recorded data in ROS/ROS2 data format from simulations and field missions
- Configuration files and simulation parameters used for the validation and reproduction of results

Wherever appropriate, these datasets will be curated for open release. Some examples include ROS2-based IMU data, RGB-D camera outputs, synthetic sensor datasets from simulations, etc. All data packages will be assigned DOI to ensure citability and persistent access.

3.3 Metadata and Interoperability Standards

To ensure interoperability and discoverability, PERSEPHONE datasets are described using standardized metadata structures. The DataCite schema has been selected as the project-wide standard, enabling structured capture of key

attributes such as dataset creator, license, temporal and spatial coverage, and technical specifications. Data are stored in open, system-independent formats, including:

- .bag files for ROS data
- .csv and .json for tabular
- .geojson, .shp, .kml, .gml for maps and positioning data
- .pcd and .ply, 3D point cloud data
- .pdf, .md, .txt for text and documentation where possible
- .jpg or .png formats for images
- .mp4 for video files.

Where conversion to open formats is not feasible, a summary documentation and metadata will still be prepared to preserve usability and traceability.

3.4 Data Review and Release Process

All datasets and research outputs intended for open release undergo internal review by WP leaders and the Innovation Management Office (IMO) (see Section 4). This ensures compliance with:

- IP ownership and licensing requirements (in coordination with the IPO)
- Data quality and completeness
- Anonymization and confidentiality protocols, where applicable

Releases are timed according to project milestones, and in cases where full datasets cannot be shared (e.g., due to industry restrictions), metadata records and high-level summaries will be published to maintain research transparency.

4 Innovation Management

PERSEPHONE, being the R&D project, has a strong focus on innovation identification and development. In D10.3 the overview of the introduced exploitation strategy has been detailed as well as project's exploitation governance (Figure 5).

Figure 5: PERSEPHONE exploitation governance, as defined in D10.3

In this the IPO is focusing on the legal and administrative aspects of intellectual property. While more specifically on patent filings, licensing, IP protection and enforcement, etc. The IMO office is responsible for taking care of strategic innovation processed, like identifying innovation ideas, developing business models and exploitation strategies and managing TRL progression.

Both offices have tight collaboration in order to ensure that innovations are protected early and align with the exploitation and project goals.

As a part of the innovation management structure four innovation teams have been established (Figure 6), where each team has its own focus and group partners with similar innovation interests and contributions. These teams operate across both offices ensuring legal protection via IPO and exploitation and impact via IMO.

Figure 6: PERSEPHONE Innovation Teams (ITs)

Innovation Team 1 is led by EPI and is centred around drilling technologies for deep and abandoned mines. While more specifically it focuses on enabling efficient and accurate near-mine exploration and extraction of mineralization.

Innovation Team 2 is led by SPE and is centred around technologies for rock mass characterization. Its ambition is to develop and validate online, in-situ technologies for ore grading.

Innovation Team 3 is led by LTU-RAI with its core focus on development of solutions for autonomous navigation in deep and abandoned mines. These technologies will enable autonomous operation of underground machines in near-mine exploration and extraction operations.

Innovation Team 4 is led by MRP with a strong focus on systems level. More specifically it innovates towards digital twin-based dynamic and interoperable geo-models for optimal planning of face drilling and extraction.

Diverse areas of expertise of the PERSEPHONE consortium form the basis for strong innovations thought-out the project duration and beyond. As the project evolves, in order to guarantee that created and newly added KERs, including background IP and foreground IP will be further commercialized the Intellectual Property Rights (IPR) will be approached in a collaborative manner following the Consortium Agreement (CA).

4.1 Background IP

At the start of the project, background intellectual property (IP) was defined and documented in the CA. As the project progresses through TRL 5 activities - such as technology validation and integration - additional background IP may become relevant to support technical development and prepare for future exploitation of Key Exploitable Results (KERs).

The IMO will periodically review and update the background IP register to ensure alignment with the evolving needs of the project and the emerging KERs.

4.2 Foreground IP

Foreground IP refers to the knowledge and results generated during the project. These outputs will be identified and documented by the designated IP lead or responsible partner throughout the implementation phase.

Regular meetings of the IMO and IPO will be used to evaluate the relevance, novelty, and potential protectability of foreground results. Where appropriate, protection measures - such as patent filings - will be planned in coordination with the contributing partners.

4.3 Commercial Rights and Stakeholder Involvement

Commercial rights to foreground IP may be granted - through licensing agreements, subcontracting arrangements, or other mechanisms - to partners interested in pursuing the commercialization of innovations beyond the project's duration. As the project progresses and innovations are further developed toward higher TRLs or market-ready solutions, end users and relevant stakeholders will

be actively engaged to ensure alignment with real-world needs and to support future exploitation pathways.

Innovation support tools

To support the IP protection LTU established a Technology Transfer Office (TTO) called LTU Business, <https://ltubusiness.com/>, which supports IP protection, patent filing and commercialization.

Currently in PERSEPHONE there is an undergoing patent filing activity coordinated by LTU-RAI that has been identified by the IT3 with a focus on supporting autonomous navigation.

5 Conclusions

The initial implementation of data management, innovation governance, and IP protection in PERSEPHONE has established a robust foundation for open science, reproducibility, and future commercialization. The release of simulation environments and open datasets demonstrates the consortium's commitment to transparency and community engagement. The establishment of the IMO and IPO, along with four innovation teams, enables structured tracking of innovations and KERs. As the project transitions into its second half, the consortium will intensify its focus on TRL advancement, stakeholder engagement, and business planning. This ensures that research outputs evolve into exploitable solutions with societal and industrial relevance.